

Original Article

Analyzing Supply leading hypothesis in Pakistan by considering Major Macro-economic variables

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Abstract

The research investigated between financial markets and development in the economy of Pakistan focusing on the Supply Leading Hypothesis taking period from 1973 to 2024 on yearly basis. According to Schumpeter theory “The Supply Leading Hypothesis 1911”, Economic growth is achieved through innovation or new products, introduce new methods of production, and exploring new markets. Therefore, financial support is inevitable, which increases savings thus, high savings lead to more investment opportunities in the economy. In later studies, the Schumpeter theory was checked that financial indicators are the cause of high economic growth or not. These studies supported the theory of Schumpeter Here, the core objective of this study, is to confirm that does Supply leading Hypothesis exists in Pakistan, whether in long and short runs. Moreover, some related variables are considered such as the Domestic Output of the Year (GDP) that is taken as the economic growth measure, including Final Consumption Expenditures (FCEX), Total Investment (TINV), Federal Government Expenditures (FGEX), Consumer Price Index (CPI), Per Capita (PC), National Savings (NS), are considered as macro-variables of the economy’s growth. Furthermore, the variables of financial markets are selected as bank credit to private sector (BCPS), market capitalization of KSE all index (MCKI), Karachi stock exchange general shares (KSEG)/ All-Share Price Index. The empirical analysis by ARDL and the causality test by Granger provided insights into short and long-runs relationships for financial Markets and growth. It was clearly seen that financial markets and other Macro-economic variables have a crucial impact in the short and long run on economic growth. The result of this research supports the objective that supply leading hypothesis occurs in Pakistan. Hence, the policies should provide strict rules and regulations to upgrade financial markets.

Keywords: Financial Development/Markets, Economic growth, Supply Leading hypothesis, ARDL, Granger causality

Introduction

The supply-leading theory was first introduced by Schumpeter in 1911. According to him, developed financial markets bring capital accumulation, innovation, and more entrepreneurs to the economy. The supply of money, inflation, exchange rate, prices of shares, rate of interest, and oil prices are the major economic variables, which have a direct relation with financial markets of any economy. Generally, the markets are the places where commodities are bought and sold at specific prices. The financial markets also do the same buying and selling of bonds and shares. While the share price is the single price of a share for some saleable equity shares of a company. Accordingly, the demand and supply of the shares determine the prices of shares. These

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markets play an important role in capital inflow for all economies whether developed and developing. The impact has been seen directly on unemployment, investment, and all the macroeconomic variables. Akbar (2011) found that stock prices and macroeconomic variables had co-integration. Adam (2008) found that prices of stock and macroeconomic variables had long-run integration at Ghana. Macmillan and Humpe (2007) suggested that prices of stock/ shares and macro-economic variables had a significant relationship. Some variables had positive, and some variables had negative relations to the stock prices in the United States. Consequently, this relationship between them has been investigated in recent years. The different results were shown by different researchers, and a dynamic relationship was found.

The policies of the governments related to financial activities and other activities for the economies bring greater influence on the financial markets and shares. It is generally known that monetary policy is the major cause of the Volatility of the stock prices and has an influence on investment and bank credits to private sector.

The share prices and inflation also move in opposite directions, it is because the actual inflation is positively correlated, with expected inflation. The share prices and money supply must be determined empirically, sometimes both are positively related and sometimes they are negatively related. Further economic growth (GDP) has a positive relationship, as all economic activities, which bring cash flow to the economy, might develop financial markets and vice versa.

The National Savings and shares prices play an important role in Pakistan's economy. The firms change their profits when investment and national saving are changed, which brings changes in share prices, therefore the firms determine the prices of stocks in the economy. Mixed results were seen in industrial economies.

The scope of the study could be seen through the direction of the variables as they show the weakness and strength of Pakistan's economy. The causality of financial markets and growth would provide knowledge to the researchers, whether to adapt the direction from the development of the financial market to economic growth or not.

The most important question of this research is whether Pakistan is experiencing the supply leading hypothesis or not. To determine causal relationship between these variables requires more research when, considering Pakistan. The long run and short run relationships from financial development (Banking sector and share market) and economic growth are necessarily required to discuss together, therefore, the main objective of this research is to check the relationship among growth, the Share Prices of all the companies registered (Karachi shares general index) and the Macroeconomic Variables for Pakistan.

Similarly, the relationship between financial development and economic growth of Pakistan, is to be checked through empirical analysis by using ARDL model and Granger Causality, to verify the supply-leading hypotheses

1.1: Variables of the research:

The variables are divided into two categories, first category is financial markets in which the Karachi stock exchange general index (KSEG), Bank credit to private sector (BCPS), Market Capitalization of KSE all index (MCKI) as variables are taken. In Second category the Macro-Economic Variables are, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Final Consumption Expenditures (FCEX), Total Investment (TINV), Federal Government expenditures (FGEX), Consumer price index (CPI), Per Capita Income (PC), National Savings (NS). Gross Domestic product is the dependent variable; however, all other variables are independent variables.

Literature Review

Research conducted in the past documented relationships that exist between stock prices and economic variables or financial markets and economic growth. Such relationships found their most appropriate fit in the Supply Leading hypothesis framework. Theoretical literature goes back to Schumpeterian theory (1911).

According to Murinde and Eng (1994), In this study, the country Singapore adopted strategies to restructure the financial sector, for this purpose the variables Bank's Development and Monetized sector were undertaken. The Supply leading hypothesis was verified through the Bi-Variate VAR model, Granger Causality test, and Co-integration.

Ibrahim (1999) checked the relation between prices of stocks and macro-economic variables, that are, industrial production (IP), supply of money, the domestic credit aggregate (CRED), and the official reserves (RES), consumer price index (CPI), and rate of exchange. Here, the period is taken from January 1977 to June 1996 for empirical analysis. The Co-integration and Granger Causality tests were performed. The results showed that causality was found in the short and the long run, which supported the supply leading hypothesis.

Levine (2005) utilized sample, consisting of 77 economies and the time was from 1960 to 1989. It suggests that the development of the financial sector is important for development in the economy. There was only Uni-directional relationship, which was from financial sector to growth.

According to Gan et al. (2006), In this study, the stock market of New Zealand and economic variables were examined. The variables were shares price index (NZSE40), Money Supply, Inflation (CPI), Exchange Rate, GDP, short and long terms rate of interest, Retail Oil Prices from domestic side. The data was taken from the years 1990 to 2003, every January. The quarterly data was taken for CPI, GDP, and domestic Retail Oil Prices. The empirical analysis was investigated by multi-variate, cointegration and causality test by Granger. These methods determined the relation between the prices of shares of (NZSE40) and macroeconomic variables. To check the shocks, variance decomposition and impulse response tests were utilized. It was concluded that inflation (CPI) had a negative relation with NZSE40, while other macroeconomic variables had a long run relation with NZSE40. Another fact was seen that NZSE did not have a leading position as compared to other developed countries' stock markets. It was checked through the Granger Causality test. The shocks had the same impact on CPI, Exchange Rate, Long Run Rate of interest, and Gross domestic product (GDP), as other developed nations' stock markets had. In the end, the research concluded that Consumer price index (CPI), Rate of exchange, Rate of interest, GDP, and money Supply determine NZSE40. The investor must consider the macro-economic variables.

Odhiambo (2007) checked the relationship between financial market's development and growth. In SSA countries. The GDP per capita was used for measuring growth. The variables which measured financial development were the ratio of broad money M^2 to GDP, the ratio of currency, and the ratio of bank claims on private sector to GDP. Empirical analysis was done through Johansen's Cointegration and Causality test by Granger. It was found that the demand following hypothesis was strong in South Africa, Kenya, accordingly in Tanzania, the supply leading hypothesis was strong.

Adam and Tweneboah (2008), the relationship was examined between macro-economic variables, which were inflation, the rate of interest, oil prices, the exchange rate, the inward FDI, and the stock market of Ghana. The data was taken from 1991 to 2007. Johansen's co-integration vector error correction model was taken for empirical analysis. It was concluded by the methodology that the stock market of Ghana, inward FDI, and macroeconomic variables showed a significant relationship. It was also observed through the error correction model that investors were getting extraordinary profits by using past values.

Hasan et al. (2008) analyzed the relationship between the Equity Market of developed countries and the Karachi Stock Exchange, this data consisted of data from 2000 to 2006. The countries include the United States of America, United Kingdom, Canada, Germany, Italy, Australia, Japan, and France. When we look at the results, the result showed that no co-integration was found between Karachi Stock Exchange and other markets except for the market of Japan and France. The Karachi stock market was independent of its innovation. Only the US and UK markets had some influence on the Karachi stock market.

Estrada et al. (2010) explained the relation between financial development and economic growth. In the early 90s, Asia had a diversified financial system in 125 countries. The period was from 1987 to 2008, or 21 years. The cross-country regression was applied and the results showed that whatever variables were used, whether total liquid liabilities, stock market or bank credit, the financial development has a positive effect on real per capita GDP growth. In the end, it was concluded that compared to the developed countries developing

countries' growth relies on the development of financial development. This study supported the supply leading hypothesis.

Singh (2010) discusses the causal relationship between the economic variables, and the stock market index had been explored. The variables were the sale price index (WPI), the Index of production of industries (IIP), and the exchange rate. The data was used on monthly rates, from April 1995 to March 2009, and was taken for applying unit root, correlation, and Granger causality test. It was concluded that the IIP variable had a causal relation with the stock market. The WPI variable had a unilateral relation with the stock market. We also found strong correlation of these two variable with the stock market of India. (Rachdi & Mbarek, 2011), investigated that economic growth (GDP per capita) and financial development had a strong and positive relationship, and had a bi-directional relationship. The evidence was taken from empirical data, which was taken from 1990 to 2006. The panel data cointegration and GMM methods used for empirical analysis. It was concluded through the error correction model that OECD countries had a bi-directional relationship, while in MENA countries, the relationship was uni-directional from financial development to economic growth. The developing countries had Uni-directional causality.

Akbar et al. (2012) explained the relation between macro-economic variables and the KSE 100. The research was conducted starting from January 1999 all the way upto June 2008. The empirical analysis was done by error-correction tests, Granger Causality Test, and the Integration Techniques for the long run. The Uni-directional relationship exists between macro-economic variables and the stock prices. The prices of stocks were positively related to short-term rates of interest and the supply of money. It was also analyzed that stock prices had a negative relation with inflation and foreign exchange reserves.

Balago (2014) analyzed the relationship between economic growth and financial development. The data was taken from 1990 to 2009. The empirical methods that were Johansen's cointegration, OLS, and vector error correction models were also applied on the data. The variables, i.e., total market capitalization, foreign direct investment, and credits of the banking sector were selected for analyzing this relationship. The result shows that all these variables had a positive influence on Gross Domestic Product, or the financial sector brings a positive impact on economic growth.

Bibi et al. (2014) examined the relationship between financial development and Economic growth. The variables selected for empirical analysis were exchange rate, foreign direct investment, exports, imports, inflation, and trade openness. The empirical analysis was done through DOLS. Dynamic ordinary least square and through Johansen's co-integration for the period of 31 years from 1980 to 2011. The study found that the long-run relationship existed between financial development and Economic growth. It was concluded that import substitutes could reduce the negative effect of trade openness, and trade surplus would be created, this trade surplus and foreign direct investment would boost economic growth more.

Ali (2014) explored the connection between the Karachi Stock Exchange and the interest rate. From 2004 to 2013. The regression and descriptive analysis suggested that the interest rate and the Karachi stock market had a negative relationship. It was also discovered that inflation would have a negative relation with the stock market.

Shahid and Kamran (2015) explored that the macro-economic factors, including the producer price index, the consumer price index (inflation), exports, imports, gold and silver prices, had a significant relationship with stock prices. The stock prices were taken from the 30 companies of the KSE-100 index, this study covered the period from 2005 to 2014. The long run relationship was checked through Johansen's cointegration, and Causality was checked by Granger's causality test. In the end it was concluded that the long- run causality existed between macroeconomic variables and stock prices.

Shahbaz et al. (2016) emphasized the macroeconomics determinants of the Pakistan's stock market. The data was analyzed from 1974 to 2010. The ARDL approach, cointegration, and the VECM were used for checking relationships in the long run. These methods were applied to macroeconomic variables. The variables inflation, financial development, investment, trade openness, and economic growth were selected to check Causality. The results suggested that inflation, economic growth, financial development, and investment

increased the development of the stock market, while trade openness decreased the stock market development. These increases and decreases showed the

Causality among macroeconomic variables and the development of the stock market in Pakistan. In this study the growth brings development in the financial sector of Pakistan.

According to Karimo and Ogbonna (2017), the research was done to check the causality between the financial sector and the economic growth. The Granger causality test showed that the Supply leading hypothesis was observed in Nigeria. The research suggested to remove obstacles and provide loan facilities to the private sector and bring investment in the economy by building up the confidence of investors.

Abbas et al. (2022) analyzed the relation between growth in economy, economic inequality, and financial development. 44 different countries were investigated to check the relationship between Financial Development and Economic Growth, while 42 countries were considered to check the relation between economic growth and economic inequality. The period was from 1995 to 2018, the ARDL approach was used for estimation. It was concluded that financial development plays a positive part in economic growth in all the countries, this is in the long run, but the upper middle-income countries have this positive relationship, which was more important. The two-way U-shaped relationship also existed and was observed through Granger Causality and VECM.

Zeeshan (2022) investigated the relation between macroeconomic variables, including the inflation rate, foreign direct investment, exchange rate, GDP, and stock market returns. The data was used for empirical study from 2006 to 2018, for every month. It was observed through OLS model that there existed a relationship between macroeconomic variables and the stock market on the KSE-100 index. The interest rate, foreign direct investment, and exchange rate had a Positive relation with the Stock Exchange of Pakistan. On the contrary, inflation played a negative role with the Pakistan stock exchange. So, the strong relationship could be observed between them, whether positive or negative.

Conceptual Framework

Author's Tabulation

Research Methodology

Collection of Data from the study

The research analyzes the relationship of financial development and economic growth within Pakistan by studying time series data taking from 1973 to 2024 on annual basis. The Karachi Stock Exchange General Index (KSEG), Bank Credit to the Private Sector and Market Capitalization Karachi Index serve as the financial market indicators, while Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Final Consumption Expenditures (FCEX), Total Investment (TINV) alongside Federal Government Expenditures (FGEX), Consumer Price Index (CPI), Per Capita Income (PC) and National Savings (NS) are macro-economic variables and fundamental economic growth indicators. The secondary data for the above variables has been collected from authentic sources that are the Statistical bulletin on the website of State Bank of Pakistan, the website of Economics survey, the website of Federal bureau of statistics Pakistan.

Table1 Data Collection and Sources

Gross Domestic Product	(Dependent Variable)	(GDP)
Consumers Price Index	(Independent Variable)	(CPI)
Final Consumption Expenditures	(Independent Variable)	(FCEX)
Federal Government Expenditures	(Independent Variable)	(FGEX)
KSE All shares	(Independent Variable)	(KSEG)
Broad Money	(Independent Variable)	(LM2)
Market Capitalization of all share index	(Independent Variable)	(LMCKI)
Market turn overs of stock market	(Independent Variable)	(MTOS)
Per Capita	(Independent Variable)	(PC)
Total Investment	(Independent Variable)	(TINV)
Bank credit to private sector	(Independent Variable)	(BCPS)
National Savings	(Independent Variable)	(NS)
Exchange rate	(Independent Variable)	(EXR)

Author's Tabulation

In table 1, the data of variables has been collected from the websites of State Bank of Pakistan, Pakistan Bureau of Statistics and Economic Survey of Pakistan. (compiled by author).

Variables of Pakistan's Financial Market

Karachi stock exchange and general index show the performance of listed companies and their share prices. From 1973 to 2025 it showed a slow upward trend in the long run but showed volatility in the short run due to political instability, economic issues, covid and lack of investors' confidence.

Bank credit to private sector shows upward trend since 1973 to 2025 .in some years it was limited due to nationalization, regulations on banking sector, global crisis covid-19, high inflation, high interest rate but it was also seen that it increased due to low interest rate, increased private investment, and low inflation. It played a positive role in the growth of the economy.

Market capitalization of KSE all index: It shows the overall size of the stock market and measures the performance of the stock market. Since 1973, in Pakistan it provided the resource allocation, wealth creation, attracted FDI, increased revenue of the government, developed the financial sector and brought growth.

Macro-Economic Variables of Growth

Here are the Macro- economic variables which are indirectly or directly connected to the growth of the economy of Pakistan.

Gross Domestic Products (GDP): Provides the true picture of the growth of the economy. Since 1973 to date, Pakistan's GDP faced many fluctuations and average growth rate was estimated between 4% to 5% per Annum. The factors involved for low Growth rate were political instability, nationalization, improper infra structure, low savings and investments, energy crisis, corruption, poor human capital, high population.

Final Consumption Expenditures: In this the consumption expenditures of the private sector, the government sector and the non-profit organizations are included. Pakistan has rising trend in it since 1973 to date. The main causes are inflation, high population, low savings, low investment, high government expenditures on developmental and non-developmental projects, corruption, and energy crisis. Basically, the economy has become consumption led economy rather than an investment-led economy.

Total Investment: Investment of any economy shows a clear picture of its growth. In Pakistan since 1973 to date, the investment showed a declining trend except in some years, when economic reforms were introduced, CPEC, and political stability boosted it, but still the investment GDP ratio remained low as the savings were not increased to a satisfactory level, energy crisis, weak institutions, debt repayment, hindered investment. So, the clear picture of investment showed less contribution to the growth of Pakistan.

Expenditures of Federal Government: In the early years of Pakistan from 1973, the government expenditures were relatively low after few years they began rising and still have a rising trend. The major causes of it were Nationalization, increased defense expenditures, high debt repayment, political instability, infra-structure development, poverty alleviation programs, Fiscal deficit measures, IMF policies, and energy crisis.

Consumer price index: This index reflects the inflationary trends in the economy. Since 1973, in Pakistan, it has consistent rising trend. The major causes were the increase in oil prices globally, political instability, fiscal disparities, high prices of food, energy crisis, devaluation of currency. Drastically inflation rate increased to 30% in 2022 and 2023, this was called a chronic inflation in the history of Pakistan.

Per Capita Income: The Per capita income is the average annual income of an individual in any country. In Pakistan it increased gradually but with a slow pace. While, from 1973 to 1999 , the increasing trend was so slow and inconsistent due to nationalization, political instability, low growth of industries, inflation but in early 2000s the slow trend changed and the per capita increased with fast pace. Fortunately, it happened due to economic reforms, privatization, remittances, and expansion in the service sector. The overall conclusion shows that increase in per capita income in Pakistan was inconsistent and had slow and fast trends.

National Savings: The National savings of Pakistan have always been remained low to the requirement of the economy. The government of Pakistan took different initiatives and policies to raise them, but the results were not fruitful. The key factors for low savings are consumption-oriented economy, low incomes, high taxes, inflation, debt burden, lack of prospects, lack of confidence on investors and corruption.

Models of Research study

ARDL and ECM model

Several econometric methods in this research analyze both time-span relationships together with trends that operate within short and long timeframes.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is a statistical procedure used to ascertain the stationarity or non-stationarity of a certain time series.

The research adopts the Error Correction Model (ECM) to study financial market interactions with economic growth patterns. The ARDL(ECM) showed cointegration equations with statistical significance at a 0.05 level while refuting the null hypothesis of long-term financial market index and economic growth relationship.

(Granger causality) method evaluates which way financial market variables affect economic development. The analysis does not confirm the supply-leading hypothesis in the long and short run by showing no directional causes between financial market expansion and economic growth. The model diagnostics prove that the conclusions are not reliable and stable. The analysis used the LM test to confirm auto-correlation.

A complete econometric investigation analyzes in detail how Pakistan's financial sector development interacts with economic growth. The results demonstrate that economic state serves as an essential base, but financial markets also act upon economic indicators. This research supports Supply Leading Hypothesis in Pakistan through the evidence of financial market advancement becoming essential for economic growth.

Model 1 of the research Study.

The following model is to be estimated.

$$\text{GDP} = f(\text{GDP}, \text{FCEX}, \text{TINV}, \text{FGEX}, \text{CPI}, \text{PC}, \text{NS}, \text{KSEG}) \quad \text{Eq 1}$$

$$\text{LGDP}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LFCEX}_t + \beta_2 \text{LTINV}_t + \beta_3 \text{LFGEX}_t + \beta_4 \text{LCPI}_t + \beta_5 \text{LPC}_t + \beta_6 \text{LNS}_t + \beta_7 \text{LKSEG}_t + \epsilon_t \quad \text{Eq 1.1}$$

General Eq1 of ARDL, model 1:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LGDP}_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \beta_2 \text{LFCEX}_{t-1} + \beta_3 \text{LTINV}_{t-1} + \beta_4 \text{LFGEX}_{t-1} \\ & + \beta_5 \text{LCPI}_{t-1} + \beta_6 \text{LPC}_{t-1} + \beta_7 \text{LNS}_{t-1} + \beta_8 \text{LKSEG}_{t-1} + \beta_{11} \sum \text{DLGDP}_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_{22} \sum \text{DLFCEX}_{t-1} + \beta_{33} \sum \text{DLTINV}_{t-1} + \beta_{44} \sum \text{DLFGEX}_{t-1} + \beta_{55} \sum \text{DLCPI}_{t-1} + \beta_{66} \sum \text{DLPC}_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_{77} \sum \text{DLNS}_{t-1} + \beta_{88} \sum \text{DLKSEG}_{t-1} + \lambda \text{ECT} + \epsilon_t \quad \text{Eq 1.} \end{aligned}$$

To explain the relationship between economic growth in Pakistan and financial development, the Error correction model (ECM) combined lag values of the variables. The variables were made smooth through Logarithms. The time of model is explained by subscript t. The long run effect is represented by coefficients β_1 to β_8 . Further, the coefficients from β_{11} to β_{88} represent the effect of short term. The coefficient λ is the rate of adjustment parameter. If the minus sign is detected in it, the model stable in the long run and shows the convergence to the equilibrium

Results and Discussion of Model 1:

Table 2: Unit Root Test (ADF Test).

In table 2, the Unit Root Test (ADF), the research finds that all variables display non-stationary patterns at their original form or at level I(0) but transform into stationary series upon applying the first differentiation process which confirms I(1) integration. Identification is done by ADF. Since the p-value of the ADF test at level was >0.05 , therefore we may accept H_0 of a unit root. This showed that the series had unit roots. All the variables LGDP, LFCEX, LTINV, LFGEX, LCPI, LPC, LNS, LMCKI, LBCPS and LKSEG were stationary at first difference order or integrated at first difference I(1), therefore stationarity of all the variables exists on the first difference

Table 2: Unit Root Test (ADF Test).

ADF Statistics				
At Level			At 1 st Difference	
Variables	t-Value	P-Value	t-Value	P-Value
LGDP	0.278084	0.9748	-4.9753	0.0001
LCPI	-0.8824	0.7860	-6.0273	0.0000
LFCEX	-0.8337	0.8007	-6.5524	0.0000
LFGEEX	-0.2935	0.9184	-7.7322	0.0000
LKSEG	-0.0844	0.9454	-7.8227	0.0000
LMCKI	-0.7600	0.8216	-6.9298	0.0000
LPC	-0.6007	0.8611	-8.9546	0.0000
LTINV	-2.1528	0.2257	-5.5943	0.0000
LBCPS	-2.5897	0.1025	-3.6357	0.0086
LNS	-1.5410	0.5048	-8.6803	0.0000

Author's calculations

ARDL (Bound test)

Here in table 3, the F-statistic value at 3.29 shows a long-run relationship among variables as it resides above the 5% level of significance. The F stat result of 3.29 lies above the determined upper limits so the outcome is confirmed for a long-term relationship.

Table 3. Bound Test:

Model	Lag Order	Value	Significance.	Lower boundary	Upper boundary
LGDP= c+LFCEX+LTINV+ LFGEX+LCPI+LPC+LNS +LKSEG	1	3.2955	10%	1.92	2.89
			5%	2.17	3.21
			2.5%	2.43	3.51
			1%	2.73	3.9

Author's calculations

ARDL and Error Correction Model.

Coint eq 2:

$$\begin{aligned}
 LGDP_t = & 0.0966 (0.0177) + 0.3902LFCEX_{t-1} (1.668) + 0.1094LTINV_t (0.7162) + 0.4309 LFGEX_t (2.4548) + \\
 & 0.0523 LCPI_t (0.4818) + (-0.1168) LPC_t (-0.3572) + 0.1173LNS_t (0.7524) + 0.0788 LKSEG_t (1.9528) + \\
 & 0.1076 \sum DLGDP_{t-1} (1.3300) + 0.3563 \sum DLGDP_{t-2} (4.1397) + 0.1651 \sum DLTINV_t (3.0939) \\
 & + 0.1030 \sum DLFGEEX_t (2.3492) + 0.1329 \sum DLCPI_t (4.0179) + 0.1455 \sum DLCPI_{t-1} (3.4424) + \\
 & 0.0615 \sum DLPC_t (1.5240) + 0.0166 \sum DLNS_t (0.6177) + (-0.0204) \sum DLNS_{t-1} (-0.8716) + \\
 & 0.0787 \sum DLNS_{t-2} (3.2838) + (-0.0028) \sum DLKSEG_t (-0.2746) + 0.0092 \sum DLKSEG (0.8546)_{t-1} + \\
 & (-0.0312) \sum DLKSEG (-2.9397)_{t-2} + (-0.0458) \sum DLKSEG (-3.6213)_{t-3} + (-0.4025) ECT (-6.2571) + \epsilon t
 \end{aligned}$$

Eq 2.

In table 4, The ARDL short term and ECM -long term model findings show that DLGDP (-2), DLTINV, DLFGEEX, DLCPI, DLPC (-1), DLKSEG (-2), DLKSEG (-3) are significant and in the short run denotes growth, but the speeds of adjustment of every variable is different respectively. On the other hand, DLGDP (-1), DLPC, DLNS (-1), DLKSEG, DLKSEG (-1) showed insignificance. In short run the Karachi stock exchange is alone not able to increase growth in the economy of Pakistan as it does not prove the significance of it in current year, it is while significant on its second lag and third lag in short term. It is also significant in the long term too. Therefore, the financial market shows a long-term relationship with growth but for the short-term adjustment, the growth depends on the past two years' lags of KSEG.

The examination of long run (ECT) in combination with robustness checks should be performed to verify whether variables can maintain a stable equilibrium relationship. Here, only LFGEX($p=0.0214$), LKSEG ($p= 0.0621$) at 5% level of significance showed long run relationship. On other side LFC EX $p= (0.1077)$ at 10% level of significance level, showed a weak long-term relationship. Except for these variables no cointegration exists in other variables in this model. All the variables in this analysis show insignificant effects on long-term outcomes. A long-run equilibrium correction function does not allow GDP to gradually return to its path if it deviates from its long-term trajectory.

As the cointegration equation showed that it is significant and it also showed the adjustment rate, and the sign shows the convergence from equilibrium. Therefore, the model indicates analysis for short and long term.

Further, R-squared value of 86.9% in the model indicates complete statistical strength with an extensive portion of GDP fluctuations being attributed to the contributing variables. The model exhibits strong fitness. This shows that dependent variables have 86.9% variation, and this variation is due to the variables mentioned in models as independent. Our model results indicate that independent variables together affect GDP level. Similarly, the test result of Durbin-Watson (2.16) confirms the significance of the model statistically.

Table 4: ARDL (Long Run) /EC (Short Run). (3,0,1,1,1,2,3,4):

Coefficients for short run in ARDL model				
Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t- Stats	Probability
D(LGDP(-1))	0.1076	0.0810	1.3300	0.1955
D(LGDP(-2))	0.3563	0.0860	4.1397	0.0003
D(LTINV)	0.1651	0.0533	3.0940	0.0048
D(LFGEX)	0.1030	0.0438	2.3492	0.0270
D(LCPI)	0.1330	0.0330	4.0179	0.0005
D(LPC)	0.0615	0.0403	1.5240	0.1400
D(LPC(-1))	0.1455	0.0422	3.4224	0.0020
D(LNS)	0.0166	0.0269	0.6177	0.5423
D(LNS(-1))	-0.0204	0.0234	-0.8716	0.3917
D(LNS(-2))	0.0787	0.0240	3.2838	0.0030
D(LKSEG)	-0.0028	0.0105	-0.2746	0.7858
D(LKSEG(-1))	0.0092	0.0108	0.8546	0.4009
D(LKSEG(-2))	-0.0312	0.0106	-2.9397	0.0070
D(LKSEG(-3))	-0.0458	0.0126	-3.6213	0.0013
CointEq(-1)*	-0.4025	0.06434	-6.2571	0.0000
EC = LGDP - (0.0966 + 0.3902LFC EX + 0.1094LTINV + 0.4310LFGEX + 0.0523LCPI - 0.1169LPC + 0.1174LNS + 0.0789LKSEG)				

Coefficients for Long run ARDL				
Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t- Stats	Probability
LFC EX	0.3902	0.2338	1.6686	0.1077
LTINV	0.1094	0.1527	0.7162	0.4805
LFGEX	0.4309	0.1755	2.4548	0.0214
LCPI	0.0523	0.1086	0.4818	0.6341
LPC	-0.1168	0.3271	-0.3572	0.7239
LNS	0.1173	0.1560	0.7524	0.4588
LKSEG	0.07890	0.0404	1.9528	0.0621
C	0.0966	5.4539	0.0177	0.9860

R-squared	0.8694	Mean dependent var	0.1395
Adjusted R-squared	0.8140	S.D. dependent var	0.0545
S.E. of regression	0.0235	Akaike info criterion	-4.4128
Sum squared resid	0.01840	Schwarz criterion	-3.8281
Log likelihood	120.9099	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-4.1919
Durbin-Watson stat	2.16565		

Author's calculations.

Note: the significance level is 1%, 5%, and 10%.

3.6.4: Granger Causality test

Table:5 shows that LFCEX granger causes LGDP, but LGDP does not granger cause LFCEX, so this shows one-way causal relationship, and the direction is from LFCEX to LGDP. LTINV does not granger cause LGDP, but LGDP granger causes LTINV, again it's a one-way causal relation and it has a direction from LGDP to LTINV, moreover, LFGEX and LGDP both do not granger cause on each other, therefore no relationship exists between them. Moreover, LCPI does not have a Granger causality with LGDP, while LGDP has granger causality with LCPI, therefore it shows a one-way causality, and the direction is from LGDP to LCPI. On the other hand, the variable LPC granger causes LGDP, but LGDP does not Granger cause LPC, so one way relationship exists, and the direction is from LPC to LGDP. Contrarily, the LNS does not granger cause LGDP, but LGDP granger causes LNS, again the relationship is one-way, and the direction is from GDP to LNS. In the last LKSEG does not have Granger causality with LGDP but LGDP has granger causality with LKSEG, like others the relationship is Uni-directional, and the direction is from LGDP to LKSEG. So, LTINV, LCPI, LNS, and LKSEG all do not granger cause LGDP. On the other way round, LGDP granger causes LTINV, LCPI, LNS, and LKSEG, some variables that are LFCEX, and LPC granger cause LGDP. All these variables have Uni- directional causality from LGDP to these variables and vice versa. Only LFGEX has no directional causality with LGDP.

Table 5: Test of Granger Causality:

Null Hypothesis	Observations	F- Stats	Probability
LFCEX does not Granger Cause LGDP	50	15.9534	6.E-06
LGDP does not Granger Cause LFCEX		0.70620	0.4989
LTINV does not Granger Cause LGDP	50	0.48643	0.6180
LGDP does not Granger Cause LTINV		4.65869	0.0145
LFGEX does not Granger Cause LGDP	50	1.53754	0.2260
LGDP does not Granger Cause LFGEX		1.97747	0.1503
LCPI does not Granger Cause LGDP	50	0.41261	0.6644
LGDP does not Granger Cause LCPI		3.37529	0.0431
LPC does not Granger Cause LGDP	50	4.96070	0.0113
LGDP does not Granger Cause LPC		2.03495	0.1425
LNS does not Granger Cause LGDP	50	0.86474	0.4280
LGDP does not Granger Cause LNS		8.20309	0.0009
LKSEG does not Granger Cause LGDP	50	0.44114	0.6461
LGDP does not Granger Cause LKSEG		3.37468	0.0431

Author's calculations

Residual Diagnostics

Heteroskedasticity Test ARCH:

Table 6, of Heteroskedasticity, ARCH test showed that there is no homoscedastic exists or no constant variance exists at the significance level of 5% for this model. This model requires changes to eliminate it.

Table6: ARCH (Heteroskedasticity test):

ARCH (Heteroskedasticity test)			
F- Stats	9.357981	Probability. F (1,45)	0.0037
Obs * R- Squared	8.091270	Prob. Chi-Square (1)	0.0044

Author’s calculations

LM Test (Breusch- Godfrey Correlation):

In Table 7, the LM test found that the probability value of F Stats is less than 0.05, which showed that autocorrelation existed in the model, therefore this model did not meet the assumption of unbiased and efficient parameter.

Table 7: LM Test:

LM Test (Breusch- Godfrey Correlation):			
F- Stats	4.44753	Probability F- (2,23)	0.0233
Obs*R-squared	13.38649	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.0012

Author’s calculations

Stability Diagnostics: CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests

The stability test was also performed by CUSUM Test and CUSUMSQ Test and the test revealed stability in the model. It is observed that in some year residual movement is outside the critical lines in CUSUMSQ plot.

Fig 1: CUSUM Test

Fig 2: CUSUMSQ Test

Conclusion

This study analyzed the complex link between economic growth in Pakistan and financial markets, specifically assessing the validity of the Supply Leading Hypothesis. The study utilized two models, with a comprehensive set of economic growth indicators, employing the Karachi Stock Exchange General Index (KSEG), Market capitalization of Karachi Index(MCKI), Bank credit to private sector (BCPS) as a proxy for financial market performance: Annual Domestic Production of the Country (GDP) measured growth in the economy of Pakistan, Final Consumption Expenditure (FCEX), Total Investment (TINV), Federal Government Expenditure (FGEX), Consumer Price Index (CPI), Per Capita Income (PC), and National Savings (NS) . These were also the variables of Macro-Economics on which the growth of the economy depends. Data spanning from 1973 to 2024 allowed the researchers to identify tendencies that play out across long-term and short-term periods. The research used ARDL and Error Correction Model (ECM) and Granger causality test after cointegrated the variables on both the models.

In Model 1, it was observed that Serial correlation and heteroskedasticity existed in the said model, therefore some changes were inevitable. Bringing this into consideration the model 2 was designed with some changes in the variables and included some more variables like bcps, lmcki, in financial markets and removed some variables that were lpc, ltinv from macro-economic variables.

According to this research share prices represented through KSEG do affect economic growth, it is also observed that financial markets have a short- and long-term impact on GDP (proxy of economic growth). Here this research proved that Supply leading hypothesis exists in Pakistan.

Note: This article is derived from the PhD dissertation of Miss Kishwer Sultana Lodhi

The research used causality tests which confirmed various direct and reciprocal effects between Macro-economic variables and financial market activities (KSEG) related to economic development measures. The research discovered the evidence that supports by showing financial markets play a substantial part in Pakistan's economic advancement and growth development. Further, the research indicates financial market expansion in Pakistan drives economic development with these macro- economic variables.

This study demonstrated Uni-directional causal relationships between economic growth and financial market indicators. The other macro-economic variables in the short run and in the long run have a causal relationship with economic growth because all areas interact and influence each other. The economic growth of Pakistan is not affected by three essential financial market's variables including LFGEX, LBCPS, LMCKI except KSEG in model 2 Future, diagnostic norms appear acceptable in the current models. The research findings conclusively show that Pakistani's economic growth depends on the existence of many not all macro-economic variables in short run and in long run. This research does support the Supply Leading Hypothesis by confirming that Karachi stock exchange does influence GDP of Pakistan. in the short run and in the long run. Further research must focus on model development that may address and detect issues while examining policy initiatives to improve financial market and economic development connections in Pakistan.

Policy Implications

The results create important policy requirements which need implementation by Pakistan's development institutions as well as economic authorities together with financial market regulators. The study confirms that financial market development has potential to create a dynamic relationship with economic development in Pakistan. The policy-making focus needs to center on financial market infrastructure improvement to drive economic development in the short run and in the long run as well. The State Bank of Pakistan (SBP) and the Security Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP) need to disclose information, reduce market irregularities and strengthen investor confidence through their regulatory role given the strong stock market-economic development relationship. The financial environment achieves stability and supports growth through enhanced market volatility and speculative trading oversight activities run by regulators. In future the Karachi Stock Exchange General Index (KSEG) will provide essential functions to drive economic development. The implementation of policies must aim to expand real estate market participation, while building knowledge about finances and creating advanced financial systems for increased investment levels. The government should provide benefits to companies that choose stock exchange listings to increase market liquidity which enables better resource distribution across the economy. The financial market performance depends heavily on the levels of domestic savings and investment so policymakers should develop incentives to boost these figures. The establishment of enhanced pension funds and mutual fund investment structures would directly save money toward productive projects to boost economic development. Price stability coupled with strategic fiscal management should be the main priorities of macroeconomic policy to establish proper conditions that support financial sector expansion. The State Bank of Pakistan needs to establish a monetary policy balance that tackles inflation without causing investment or consumer growth constraints, as economic planning is increasingly important. Financial market expansion needs policymakers to create plans that link market growth with national economic objectives for establishing a resilient economic system. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) enable the distribution of financial needs between private and public sectors for industrial development and infrastructure. Financial policies need to make private capital accessible for substantial economic projects as this action strengthens the growth-advancing relationship between growth of the economy and market development. To develop effective economic policies the government needs to implement systematic and comprehensive data analysis which requires constant assessment of financial and economic metrics and ongoing financial market evaluation. The economic policies need data-based guidance from VECM and ARDL models to create effective modifications that control economic variability. Research results establish that Pakistan's economic success requires both financial markets along with other macro-economic variables. A proper legislative framework should support financial market strength in addition to promoting economic development. The application of suggested policy measures will help Pakistan to establish an efficient financial environment that enables sustained economic growth for a longer time.

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